

1 Understanding soil organic carbon processes through functional
2 biodiversity: insights from plant and microbial interactions in
3 agricultural soils
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29

30 Abstract
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32 Soil is a vital carbon sink and a critical natural resource for humanity, especially in the context of
33 climate change. Soil organic carbon (SOC) is also a critical measure of soil health, supporting
34 biodiversity, water retention, and nutrient cycling. SOC is therefore relevant for climate resilience,
35 sustainable agriculture, and ecosystems functioning. Together, soil and plant biodiversity mediate
36 several ecosystem processes. This study investigated the role of functional diversity in SOC accrual,
37 with a particular focus on plant and microbial biodiversity in agricultural soils. The research sought to
38 answer four key questions: (i) How relevant is functional diversity in explaining variations in SOC and
39 water-extractable organic carbon (WEOC)?; (ii) How do microbial groups and plant traits interactions
40 influence SOC processes; (iii) Do farming practices affect the plant and microbial functional groups
41 relevant for SOC turnover?; (iv) What is the impact of these farming practices on SOC-related

42 functional diversity? We collected data on soil and plant biodiversity across seven experimental sites
43 in Europe and Turkey. We found that about 60% of the variability in SOC and WEOC was determined
44 by functional biodiversity. Partial least square structural equation modelling revealed that plant
45 functional groups did not have direct significant effects on SOC. Plant traits, such as specific leaf area,
46 the presence of perennials and Grass-like species, significantly influenced the bacterial and fungal
47 functional groups, which had a negative impact on SOC. Additionally, the abundance of those groups
48 were strongly affected by farming practices. To the best of our knowledge, this research is the first to
49 examine the complexity of SOC dynamics using a functional approach that integrates plant, bacterial,
50 and fungal communities. Overall, the results from this study demonstrated the key role of functional
51 biodiversity on SOC turnover, thereby calling for the integration of functionality aspects in monitoring
52 and designing sustainable soil management practices at different scales.

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54 Highlights

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- 56 - Functional diversity is extremely relevant in explaining the variance of SOC in agricultural soils.
- 57 - Plant traits and functional bacterial and fungal groups which are critical to SOC turnover were
58 identified
- 59 - Farming practices are key environmental filters able to steer the functionality of the plant and
60 microbial communities and ultimately SOC dynamics.

61 Keywords

62 Functional biodiversity, soil organic carbon, farming practices, plant functional traits, soil microbial
63 functional groups

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66 1. Introduction

67 Soil serves as an essential carbon sink and a crucial natural resource for humanity, particularly in the
68 face of climate change. Soil organic carbon (SOC) also represents an important attribute of healthy
69 soils. It provides habitat and resources to soil biodiversity, improves water retention and contributes
70 to nutrient cycling. SOC is therefore essential to tackle the challenge of climate change while
71 promoting sustainable agricultural production and enhancing ecosystem resilience.

72 Soil and plant biodiversity mediate essential ecosystem services (ES), including soil carbon cycling and
73 storage. Plants significantly influence SOC through various organic matter inputs, such as litter,
74 residues, and roots turnover (Tian et al., 2023). Notably, plant species diversity has been identified as

75 a key driver for SOC accumulation. A recent meta-analysis indicated that more diverse plant
76 communities substantially increase SOC levels compared to monoculture systems (Chen et al., 2020).
77 This trend has been observed across various pedoclimatic regions and cropping systems. As example,
78 undersown species in association with barley led to increased SOC in rhizospheric soils in a Finnish
79 cereal experiment (Domeignoz-Horta et al., 2020). In tropical forests plant diversity was shown to
80 directly and indirectly influence C storage (Li et al., 2020) while grassland studies revealed a positive
81 correlation between plant species diversity and SOC (Anacker et al., 2021).

82 Overall, SOC is strongly influenced by plant diversity, with studies suggesting that SOC levels can
83 increase by up to 2.6 times as the Shannon Index of plants’ communities rises from 0 to 2.5 (Spohn et
84 al., 2023). Although the impact of plant diversity on SOC may be climate-dependent, the benefits of
85 multispecies systems are primarily attributed to the varying qualities of organic matter provided by
86 plant residues rather than the total organic input (Spohn et al., 2023).

87 Soil microbial diversity, including bacteria and fungi, is also significantly influenced by plant diversity
88 and plays a crucial role in SOC dynamics. Different plant assemblages supply distinct types of residues
89 and root exudates, shaping the soil microbial communities which metabolize C input. Literature has
90 established strong correlations between microbial richness and SOC (Bastida et al., 2021). Microbial
91 diversity was found to be the strongest predictors for Carbon Use Efficiency (Domeignoz-Horta et al.,
92 2020), which represents one of the main determinants of soil organic C change at the global scale (Tao
93 et al., 2023). Microbial diversity indexes were also investigated as predictors for soil C mineralization
94 and hence as key factors to be included in SOC prediction models (Louis et al., 2016). Despite the value
95 of microbial diversity in soil C ecology, it has been argued that the composition and functionality of
96 soil microbial communities may be more effective in explaining how farming practices impact SOC
97 (Wooliver et al., 2022)

98 Although extensive research has focused on the role of plant and soil microbial diversity on SOC
99 dynamics, less attention has been given to the effects of plant and microbial functional diversity on
100 SOC accrual. Emerging in recent decades, the functional biodiversity approach offers a novel
101 perspective on ecological processes related to SOC. This approach characterizes plant or microbial
102 communities based on traits or groups, calculated as community-weighted mean values according to
103 species abundance (Roscher et al., 2012). This concept emerged as a more operational approach to
104 the study of plant and soil biodiversity, opening new fields of research focused on the interaction
105 between ecology and land use (Díaz et al., 2007). It has been argued that functionality of the microbial
106 and plant communities could be more relevant in explaining ecosystem functioning compared to the
107 biodiversity *per se*, particularly regarding ES and multifunctionality (Song et al., 2014). Moreover, since

108 different ES share common functional traits, employing a functional approach in agroecological
109 studies may yield significant insights on the wide role of biodiversity on ecosystem functioning and
110 management (Hanisch et al., 2020).

111 Plant traits such as Specific Leaf Area (SLA) or nutrient content have been indicated as important
112 factors to estimate plant nutrient allocation and nutrient cycling in agroecosystems. Similarly roots
113 traits have been related to soil C dynamics and plant-microorganisms' interactions (De Long et al.,
114 2019). Research conducted about 15 years ago already indicated direct and indirect impacts of plant
115 traits on SOC sequestration across various biomes (De Deyn et al., 2008).

116 Additionally, plant traits have been shown to influence soil enzymatic activities, underscoring critical
117 interactions between plant communities and microbial functional groups (Alberti et al., 2017).
118 However, a global study revealed that plant functional traits alone may not sufficiently explain the
119 complex interactions involved in SOC dynamics. Additional factors, such as pedoclimatic conditions
120 and soil biodiversity indices, are necessary to accurately explain these interactions (van der Plas et al.,
121 2020). A recent review by Jayaramaiah et al. (2024) highlighted that ecosystem functioning and ES
122 research has often overlooked plant-microbial interactions. According to the authors, future studies
123 should adopt trait-based approaches to investigate plant-microbial interactions which are essential in
124 the provision of multiple ES.

125 Finally, a broad literature demonstrated that plant and soil biodiversity are critical for soil health and
126 ecosystem stability. The interactions between soil and plant biodiversity underpin essential processes
127 that support multiple ES. In the last decades the study of functional biodiversity emerged as a new
128 lens to analyse, monitor and promote the role of the soil life and plant assemblages on ES. However,
129 the mechanisms underlying these interactions and how farmers can manage biodiversity to balance
130 environmental and productive goals remain unclear.

131 This research aims to contribute to this ongoing discussion. In the AGROECOseqC project, we collected
132 data on plant diversity and functional traits, and microbial functional diversity, to investigate their
133 effects on SOC accrual across various European locations. We also assessed the impact of different
134 farming practices on functional diversity related to SOC. This research seeks to address the following
135 research questions:

- 136 1. Is functional diversity relevant in explaining the variance of SOC and water extractable organic
137 Carbon (WEOC) in agricultural soils?
- 138 2. Given the complexity of the functional microbial groups and plants' traits, how do they
139 interact in the context of SOC processes?

- 140 3. Do farming practices have an effect on plants and microbial functional groups?
141 4. What is the impact of farming practices on the plant and microbial functional groups relevant
142 for SOC turnover?

143 2. Material and Methods

144 2.1 Sites and experimental designs

145 The study was carried out in seven experimental sites located in Italy, Lithuania, Spain, Belgium,
146 France, and Turkey. The locations covered a wide range of European pedoclimatic areas and different
147 degree of agroecological intensification ranging from cereal monocropping to organic fruit systems.
148 Specific data concerning the experimental sites are reported in Table 1. Additional info regarding the
149 experimental design and farm management can be found in Doyeni et al. (2024). All experiments were
150 carried out in randomized complete block designs with four blocks. In Belgium, Denmark, Turkey,
151 France 1 and France 2 we collected one sample per block in each treatment (n=12 for all core sites,
152 but France 2 where eight samples were collected). In Italy, Spain, and Lithuania we collected three
153 samples per block in two treatments (INC, ICC in Italy; NT, NTR in Spain; NT, NT+CC in Lithuania) to
154 compile an additional dataset (n=18 per core site) to test more robustly the effect of farming practices
155 on specific plant traits and functional groups. We therefore compiled two dataset: Experiment A
156 consisting in all the data collected and Experiment B where only the data collected in Italy, Spain and
157 Lithuania were considered.

Table 1 Location, pedoclimatic characteristics and management practices of the study sites.

Country	Site location	Climatic zone	Mean annual temperature (°C)	Mean annual rainfall (mm y ⁻¹)	Year of establishment	pH	Texture	Main crop/s	Treatments	Soil and plant sampling date	Plant sampling method
Italy	Rome, N 41° 79' 89" E 12° 57' 21"	Mediterranean-North	15.7	154	2017	6,7	Sandy clay loam	Organic apricot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INC: Compost, no tillage, spontaneous cover • ICC: Compost, tillage, mix cover crops (wheat + vetch) • BAU: Organic fertilizer, tillage, mechanical weeding 	April 2023	Soil estimation cover by species
Lithuania	Akademija, Kedainiai distr., N 55° 39' 72" E 23° 86' 11"	Nemoral	6.5	592	2013	6,7	Loam	Oil seed rape	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NT: No tillage, no cover crop • NT+CC: No tillage, cover crop • T: Tillage, no cover crop 	October 2022	Plant density by species
Spain	Alcalá de Henares, N 40°52' 34" E 3° 12' 42"	Mediterranean-South	9.1	895	1994	8	Sandy loam	Wheat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NT: No tillage wheat monocrop • NTR: No tillage, wheat-vetch-barley rotation • MT: Minimum tillage wheat monocrop 	May 2023	Soil cover estimation by species
Belgium	Gembloux, Lat.0.5606556 Long. 4.7264556	Atlantic-central	10.4	730	1959	6,8	Loamy clay	Sugar beet, wheat, barley	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SBWBFYM: Sugar beet, wheat, barley, farmyard manure, crop residues export • SBWBRC: Sugar beet, wheat, barley, cover crop and crop residues retention • SBWB: Sugar beet, wheat, barley and crop residues export 	April 2023	Plant density by species
France 1	Clermont Ferrand, N 45°46'27.03" E 3°8'31.02"	Continental	12.7	514	2016	6,1	Sandy clay loam	Wheat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GLN: Wheat + perennial cover • WGLN: Wheat + diversified cover (grasses+legumes) • WN: Wheat monoculture 	May 2023	Soil cover estimation by species
France 2	Mauguio, N 43°36'45.3" E 3°58'37.7"	Hot-summer Mediterranean climate	15.6	740	2017	6.8	Loamy clay	Cereals, legumes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TSG: Tree strip + perennial grass, no tillage • TSR: Crop rotation in agroforestry alley, tillage 	May 2023	Soil cover estimation by species
Turkey	Sanliurfa, N 36°53'12.72" E 38°55'15.04"	Anatolian	18.5	463	2022	7,8	Clay sandy loam	Tomato	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NF: Cover crop, no fungi inoculant • FC: Cover crop, fungi inoculant • NFNC: No cover crop, no fungi inoculant 	June 2023	Plant density by species

2.2 Soil and plants sampling and analysis

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Soil and plants samples were collected at the peak of green biomass (maximum nutrient uptake) at the respective experimental sites. Most of the sites were sampled in April - June 2023, but at the LAMMC site - in October 2022, considering the maximum development of cover crops. Bulk soil samples were collected from 0–20 cm depth. Four sub-samples per block were taken with a steel auger and pooled together. Visible roots and plant residues were removed manually from bulk soils. Then the samples were sieved through a 2mm sieve, homogeneously mixed and kept at -20°C for molecular analysis and 4°C for chemical analysis. Data on plant soil cover or plant density were collected with the same sampling protocol (replicates, time and area) of the soil samples.

To analyze aggregates, undisturbed soil samples were taken by a flat spade, from a 0–20 cm depth at approximately 5 cm thick ×15 cm width size to ensure at least 900 g prepared soil sample for the sieving analysis. The sample was gently broken to, approximately 1 cm³ aggregates (clumps) and impurities (stones, larger plant residues, etc.) were removed. Soil sample was air dried naturally, before sieving. 200 g of soil samples were weighed and sieved by the Retsch sieve shaker with mesh sizes 8, 5.6, 4, 2, 1, 0.5, and 0.25 mm. This was subjected to a shaking amplitude of 60 rpm and a sieving time of 2 min. After that, the soil left on each sieve is weighted. The procedure was repeated from 1 to 5 times, (depending on the soil structure) to ensure enough sample of fine and coarse aggregates for further analysis.

SOC and WEOC analyses were conducted at the Chemical Research Laboratory, at LAMMC. The SOC content was analyzed according to the Nikitin-modified Tyurin dichromate oxidation method using wet combustion at 160 °C. SOC measurement was performed using an automatic spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 590 nm, with glucose as a standard (Nikitin, 1999). The WEOC determination was performed according to the methodology guided by SKALAR, using C₈H₅KO₄ as a standard. The soil prepared for the chemical analyses was poured with distilled water at a ratio of 1:5, and the extract was prepared by shaking, centrifugation for 15 min at 4500 rpm, and filtration. After that, the automated measurement procedure was performed based on the IR detection method following UV-catalyzed persulfate oxidation under a nitrogen environment (SKALAR, The Netherlands). Each soil sample was analyzed in triplicate.

192 2.3 Plants functional traits

193 Plant traits were selected based on their ecological significance in carbon processes. These traits were
194 drawn from the weed functional traits database by Barberi et al. (2018) and additional literature
195 (Kattge et al., 2020). When the trait was not available at the species level, imputation was performed
196 at the genus or family level. The traits analyzed included canopy height (CH, maximum height at
197 maturity), specific leaf area (SLA, $\text{mm}^2 \text{mg}^{-1}$), the percentage of grass and grass-like species (GRASS,
198 %), the percentage of perennials species (PER, %), the percentage of taproot species (TAPROOT, %)
199 and the percentage of species supporting arbuscular mycorrhiza (SAM, %).

200 The CH and SLA are reliable indicators of biomass production in vegetation (Walter et al., 2019),
201 making them useful for assessing a plant's contribution to soil carbon inputs. CH is often used as a
202 proxy for aboveground biomass, as it reflects the structural and density characteristics of vegetation.
203 Similarly, SLA, which expresses the relationship between leaf area and dry mass, indicates plant
204 productivity by revealing how effectively a plant captures light for photosynthesis and biomass
205 production (Reich, 2014). Grass and grass-like species are known for their higher C:N ratio, which
206 contributes to the formation of stable soil organic matter.

207 Studies (e.g. Dessureault-Rompré, 2022) highlighted the advantages of perennial compared to annual
208 species in carbon sequestration through their robust root systems and slower root material
209 decomposition rates, which stabilize organic matter in the soil. Perennial roots and propagules also
210 act as significant carbon reservoirs. Moreover, perennial species are characterized by a lower
211 aboveground biomass production at a different temporal rhythm than annual plants translating in a
212 reduced input of chemically robust aboveground litter (Berardi et al., 2024). Taproot plants, compared
213 to fibrous root plants, may enhance C sequestration by storing C in deeper soil layers, providing
214 greater root biomass, and decomposing more slowly due to their lignified structure, contributing to
215 long-term soil carbon stability (Srivastava & Yetgin, 2024). Lastly, the SAM trait is associated with the
216 ability of plants to support mycorrhizal fungi, indicating the potential for a well-developed mycelial
217 network (Trinchera et al., 2021), which further enhances soil carbon processes.

218 2.4 Microbial DNA extraction, sequencing and processing

219 Soil DNA was extracted using the DNeasy PowerSoil Pro Kit (Qiagen, Germany) using 0.5 g of soil and
220 purified with a QIAquick Gel kit (Qiagen). The DNA quality was measured by electrophoresis on 1.5%
221 agarose gel. DNA extraction yield was quantified using a NanoDrop 2000 fluorospectrometer (Thermo
222 Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). The DNA was sequenced using the ILLUMINA miSeq technology,
223 with a paired 2x 300pb strategy at the Instituto de Parasitología y Biomedicina "Lopez-Neyra" (CSIC,
224 Spain). The libraries were constructed with the Nextera XT v2 DNA Library Preparation kit (Illumina
225 Inc., CA, USA). The V3-V4 region of bacterial 16SrRNA was amplified using the primer pair 341F (5'-
226 CCTACGGGNBGCASCAG-3') and 806R (5'-GACTACNVGGGTATCTAATCC-3') (Takahashi et al., 2014) and

227 the resulting amplicons were tagged to PNA PCR clamps to reduce mitochondrial and plastid DNA
228 amplification (Lundberg et al., 2013). The ITS2 region of fungal 18S rRNA was amplified using the
229 primer pair ITS2 – fiTS7 (5'-GTGARTCATCGAATCTTTG-3') and ITS4 (5'-TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC-3')
230 (Ihrmark et al., 2012).

231 The sequences were demultiplexed and then, quality tested using the FASTQC program v0.12.1
232 (Andrews, 2023). The raw sequences were processed using the DADA2 pipeline v1.22 (Callahan et al.,
233 2016) on R v4.1.2 (R Development Core Team, 2021). For fungal sequences, we removed the primers
234 using cutadapt v4.9 (Martin, 2011), for bacteria we trimmed the first 19 and 21 nucleotides of the
235 sequences. We also trimmed the fungal and bacterial sequences using a quality score threshold of two
236 and five respectively. No extra trimming was performed. We assigned the taxonomy to the obtained
237 ASVs using the SILVA v 138.1 (Quast et al., 2012) database for bacteria and the UNITE v 9.0 database
238 for fungi (Abarenkov et al., 2023). We removed singletons and those ASVs not assigned to a known
239 phylum and rarefied the ASV tables to the lowest sequencing depth. Finally, we calculated the
240 potential functionality of fungal and bacterial communities using the FungalTraits database (Pölme et
241 al., 2020) for fungi and the functional annotation of prokaryotic taxa database (FAPROTAX v 1.2.6)
242 (Louca et al., 2016) for bacteria. The following microbial functional groups were considered for the
243 analysis:

- 244 - C degradation bacteria: cellulolysis, chitinolysis, lignolysis, fermentation;
- 245 - Recalcitrant C degradation bacteria: xylanolysis, aromatic compound degradation,
246 hydrocarbon degradation;
- 247 - C fixation bacteria: photosynthetic_cyanobacteria, nonphotosynthetic cyanobacteria;
- 248 - Mycorrhizal fungi: arbuscular mycorrhizal, ectomycorrhizal;
- 249 - Saprotroph fungi: dung_saprotroph, litter_saprotroph, unspecified_saprotroph,
250 wood_saprotroph.

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252 [2.5 Statistical analysis](#)

253 We applied redundancy analysis (RDA) to quantify the variance explained by plant traits and microbial
254 groups on SOC and WEOC. The adjusted R^2 was calculated to obtain the variance explained by the RDA
255 (*vegan*, package). RDA was also used to identify which microbial functional groups and plant functional
256 traits were most strongly associated with SOC and WEOC, and to visualize the relationships between
257 these variables. Prior to analysis, the data were standardized and performed a stepwise exclusion of
258 factors starting with those having Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values greater than five. The
259 significance of RDA axes and all the functional traits and groups were tested through permutation test.

260 We employed Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM) to explore the causal
261 relationships between plant functional traits, fungal and bacterial functional groups, and their
262 mediation of SOC changes. Specifically, we tested the following three hypotheses: (i) plant functional
263 traits have a direct effect on SOC, (ii) fungi functional groups have a direct effect on SOC, (iii) bacteria
264 functional groups have a direct effect on SOC (iv) plant functional traits influence the microbial groups
265 related to SOC. All plant and microbial data were incorporated as factors to construct the model. To
266 address multicollinearity, we calculated the VIF and performed a stepwise exclusion of factors starting
267 with those having VIF values greater than three. Subsequently, we screened the model for indicator
268 weights, excluding factors with non-significant weights and non-significant loadings below 0.5 (Hair et
269 al., 2017). VIF, variable selection and bootstrapping were carried out with SmartPLS4.0 while we used
270 the *sempr* package in R to plot the model.

271 We also evaluated the selective effect of farming practices on all microbial and plant functional
272 groups/traits at the Italian, Lithuanian and Spanish sites using Non-Metric Multidimensional Scaling
273 (NMDS)(*vegan* package). The stress value of the NMDS ordination was assessed, and non-significant
274 dispersion was tested. Additionally, to assess the significance of the farming treatments, we used
275 PERMANOVA (permutation=999) with core sites treated as “strata” to account for site-specific effects
276 (*vegan* package).

277 We further examined how farming practices influenced the functional traits and microbial groups
278 identified in the PLS-SEM analysis. For each functional trait or group, we fitted both linear models and
279 generalized linear models using treatment and block as factors, with and without interaction terms.
280 Beta-regression was also tested for the perennial and Grass-like traits. Data concerning non
281 photosynthetic cyanobacteria and arbuscular mycorrhiza in the Lithuanian site and dung saprotroph
282 in the Spanish site, were square root transformed before the analysis. We selected the model with
283 the lowest Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) from linear, betaregression and generalized linear
284 model (gamma, gamma log and gaussian log distributions). Anova type II was used to assess models
285 without interactions, while type III Anova was employed for models with interactions. To test for
286 normality of residuals in linear models, we applied the Shapiro-Wilk test, while residual diagnostics
287 for generalized linear models was performed using the *DHARMA* package. Pairwise comparisons of
288 treatments were conducted using the Tukey HSD test (*emmeans* package), with a significance
289 threshold of 0.05.

290 All statistical analyses, unless otherwise mentioned, were conducted in R (version 4.4.1.)

291

292 3. Results

293 3.1 Is functional diversity relevant in explaining the variance of soil organic carbon and
294 water extractable carbon in agricultural fields?

295 The RDA revealed that functional diversity accounted for about 60% of the total variance (Adjusted r^2
296 = 58.1%), and the overall model was statistically significant ($p \leq 0.001$). Figure 1 offers a graphic
297 representation of the RDA while the results of the ANOVA permutation test for the included factors
298 can be found in S1. Significant plants functional traits influencing SOC and WEOC included GRASS, SLA
299 ($p \leq 0.001$) and PER ($p \leq 0.01$). Concerning microbial groups, Figure 1 suggested also that arbuscular
300 mycorrhiza ($p \leq 0.01$), dung saprotroph ($p \leq 0.01$), litter saprotroph ($p \leq 0.001$), hydrocarbon degradation
301 bacteria ($p \leq 0.01$) and fermentation bacteria ($p \leq 0.001$) had a significant negative relationship with
302 SOC.

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304 Figure 1 Redundancy analysis (RDA) of functional plant and soil traits of the Agroecoseq-C. CH= Crop Height; GRASS= Grass
305 Species; SLA= Specific Leaf Area; SAM= Support Arbuscular Mycorrhiza; TAPROOT= Taproot Species; PER= Perennial Species;
306 SOC= Soil Organic Carbon; WEOC= Water Extractable Organic Carbon. Dataset= Experiment A (n=108)

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308 3.2 Given the complexity of the functional microbial groups and plants’ traits, how do
 309 they interact in the context of SOC processes?

310 The results of the PLS-SEM are presented in Figure 2. The construct representing plant functional traits
 311 was significantly constituted by the SLA trait, the presence of Grass-like and perennial species
 312 ($p \leq 0.001$). The plant community showed a negative significant effect ($p \leq 0.001$) on both fungal and
 313 bacterial functional groups while its contribution to SOC, despite positive, was not significant. The
 314 fungal functional group construct was defined by litter saprotroph ($p \leq 0.001$), arbuscular mycorrhiza
 315 ($p \leq 0.01$) and dung saprotroph ($p \leq 0.001$). Those groups had a significant negative effect ($p \leq 0.01$) on
 316 SOC. In the bacterial functional construct, fermentation ($p \leq 0.001$) and non-photosynthetic
 317 cyanobacteria ($p \leq 0.01$) were the two significant determinants. The bacterial functional groups showed
 318 a stronger significant negative effect ($p \leq 0.001$) on SOC than fungi ($p \leq 0.01$). Overall the model
 319 explained 50% of the SOC variability (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.503$).

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322 *Figure 2 PLS-SEM on the effects of functional plant traits (PLANT_FT) and microbial functional groups (BACTERIA_FG and*
 323 *FUNGI_FG) on Soil Organic Carbon (SOC). Dataset=Experiment A (n=108). The size of the arrows between latent constructs*
 324 *(BACTERIA_FG, PLANT_FT, FUNGI_FG and SOC) indicate the path coefficient of the structural model. The thicker the arrow,*
 325 *the stronger the relationship. Arrows from indicators to latent constructs represent factor loadings. A thicker arrow means*
 326 *a higher loading, showing that the indicator strongly reflects the construct. Dotted lines indicate negative effects. NP= Non-*
 327 *photosynthetic. **= $p \leq 0.01$; ***= $p \leq 0.001$*

328 3.3 Do farming practices play an effect on the plants and microbial functional groups?

329 The NMDS analysis of plant traits and microbial functional groups demonstrated that farming practices
 330 had a significant impact on plant and microbial functional traits especially in Italy (Figure 3). Results of

331 the PERMANOVA (Table 2) clearly showed that treatment ($p \leq 0.001$) had a significant effect on plants
 332 traits and microbial functional groups related to soil C, independently of the experimental site.

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335 *Figure 3 NMDS on the effect of farming practices on plant and microbial functional traits associated with SOC. CS1= Italy;*
 336 *CS5= Spain, CS7=Lithuania. T1 refers to INC, NT, NT In Italy, Spain and Lithuania, respectively. T2 refers to ICC, NTR, NT+CC*
 337 *in Italy, Spain and Lithuania, respectively. Stress=0.13.Dataset= Experiment B (n=54).*

338 *Table 2 Results of Permanova analysis. Data were stratified by experimental site. Dataset= Experiment B (n=54)*

	Df	Sum of square	R2	F	Pr(>F)
Treatment	1	0,0611	0,0458	2,4992	***
Residual	52	1,2706	0,9541		

339 *** significant at $p \leq 0.001$.

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342 3.4 What is the impact of farming practices on the plant functional traits and microbial 343 groups affecting SOC turnover?

344 Table 4 shows the results of the regression models used to analyse plant traits and microbial functional
 345 groups which significantly formed the construct of the PLS-SEM (Figure 2). Treatments had a strong
 346 effect on plant traits only in the Italian site (Table 4). Both perennials and SLA ($p \leq 0.001$) were higher
 347 under INC (Table 5). Perennials were almost 7 times higher under INC (Perennials = $57.7 \pm 4.4\%$)
 348 compared to ICC (Perennials = $7.3 \pm 2.1\%$), while a lower difference between the treatments was

349 observed for SLA (Table 5). No perennial plants were found in the Spanish experimental sites.
 350 Treatment did not affect Grass-like species in the experimental sites under study.

351 *Table 3 Results from the Analysis of variance for the plant, bacteria and fungi functional groups which resulted significant in*
 352 *the PLS-SEM model (n=18 per each site). Dataset= Experiment B (n=54)*

	Functional trait/group	Treatment	Block	Treatment x Block	Model distribution
Italy	Perennials	***	ns	-	Betaregression
	Specific Leaf Area	***	ns	-	Gamma Log
	Grass-like	ns	ns	-	Betaregression
	Fermentation	***	ns	-	Gamma Log
	NP Cyanobacteria	***	ns	**	Normal
	Litter Saprotroph	ns	ns	-	Gamma Log
	Arbuscular Mycorrhiza	ns	*	*	Normal
	Dung Saprotroph	**	***	*	Gamma Log
Spain	Perennials	-	-	-	-
	Specific Leaf Area	ns	ns	ns	Normal
	Grass-like	ns	ns	-	Betaregression
	Fermentation	ns	ns	*	Normal
	NP Cyanobacteria	**	ns	-	Normal
	Litter Saprotroph	**	ns	-	Gamma Log
	Arbuscular Mycorrhiza	***	ns	-	Gamma Log
	Dung Saprotroph	***	ns	-	Normal
Lithuania	Perennials	ns	ns	-	Betaregression
	Specific Leaf Area	ns	ns	-	Gamma Log
	Grass-like	ns	ns	-	Normal
	Fermentation	ns	***	***	Gamma Log
	NP Cyanobacteria	ns	*	**	Normal
	Litter Saprotroph	ns	ns	-	Normal
	Arbuscular Mycorrhiza	*	*	*	Normal
	Dung Saprotroph	ns	ns	-	Gamma Log

353 ns = not significant. - = no interaction tested in the model. *, **, *** significant at $p \leq 0.05$, $p \leq 0.01$ and $p \leq 0.001$,
 354 respectively.

356 All the bacterial functional groups were significantly affected by the management practices in
 357 Lithuania and Italy (Table 4 and 5). Cover cropping increased the abundance of cellulolytic bacteria by
 358 about 61% and 42.5% in Italy and Lithuania, respectively. Overall diversification practices tended to
 359 increase the fermentation bacterial groups across all the three sites. Higher abundances of this
 360 bacterial functional group were found under cover cropping in Italy and Lithuania (only in block 2) and
 361 crop rotation (only in block 3) in Spain (Table 5). Non-photosynthetic cyanobacteria were higher under
 362 ICC compared to INC in Italy only in the first block, while a significant reduction of this bacterial group
 363 under crop rotation was observed in Spain (Table 5). Not clear trends were observed in Lithuania,

364 where non-photosynthetic cyanobacteria abundance varied according to both treatment and block,
365 recording higher and lower abundances under cover cropping in block 2 and 3, respectively.
366 Concerning fungal groups, litter saprotrophs were significantly affected by the management practices
367 only in Spain, where crop rotation boosted this fungal groups by almost 55% (Table 5). Diversification
368 practices significantly affected arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi in all the experimental sites. In Spain we
369 observed a negative effect of crop rotation on mycorrhizal groups. A similar effect was found in
370 Lithuania and Italy under cover cropping. Nevertheless, in these sites the effect of the treatment was
371 found only in one block (Table 5). Despite the ANOVA underlined a significant effect of practices on
372 dung saprophytes fungi, in Italy the post-hoc test did not highlight any significant differences. A
373 different scenario was observed in Spain where dung saprophytes decreased by 63% under crop
374 rotation, while no differences were recorded in Lithuanian site (Table 5).

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Table 4 Results of the Tuckey HSD test carried out on functional traits/groups where treatment and/or the interaction between treatment and block was significant. Microbial functions are expressed as average relative abundance. Treatments indicated by different letters are significantly different at $p < 0.05$. Numbers following the \pm denote standard errors of the mean. INC= Natural Cover and Compost; ICC= Cover crop and Compost, NT= No tillage, NTR= No tillage + crop rotation, NT+CC= No tillage + Cover crop. Dataset= Experiment B

Functional trait/group	Treatment		Treatment x Block						
	INC	ICC	INC X Block 1	INC X Block 2	INC X Block 3	ICC X Block 1	ICC X Block 2	ICC X Block 3	
Italy	Perennials (%)	57.7±04.40 a	7.3±2.10 b	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Specific Leaf Area (m ² g ⁻¹)	28.17±0.46 a	23.91±0.39 b	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Grass-like	ns	ns	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Fermentation	1.54±0.11 b	2.33±0.16 a	-	-	-	-	-	-
	NP Cyanobacteria	0.008±0.003 b	0.023±0.003 a	0.00±0.005 b	0.009±0.0.005 a	0.015±0.005 a	0.044±0.005 a	0.009±0.005 a	0.015±0.005 a
	Litter Saprotroph	ns	ns	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Arbuscular Mycorrhiza	ns	ns	0.16±0.04 a	0.20±0.04 a	0.02±0.04 a	0.07±0.04 a	0.01±0.04 b	0.02±0.04 a
	Dung Saprotroph	2.74±0.27 a	2.49±0.25 a	4.51±0.77 a	1.50±0.26 a	3.05±0.52 a	2.31±0.39 b	1.87±0.32 a	3.60±0.61 a
	NT	NTR	NT X Block 1	NT X Block 2	NT X Block 3	NTR X Block 1	NTR X Block 2	NTR X Block 3	
Spain	Perennials (%)	Nd	Nd	Nd	Nd	Nd	Nd	Nd	Nd
	Specific Leaf Area (m ² g ⁻¹)	ns	ns	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Grass-like	ns	ns	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Fermentation	ns	ns	4.95±0.32 a	4.09±0.32 a	4.00±0.32 b	4.41±0.32 a	4.95±0.32 a	5.47±0.32 a
	NP Cyanobacteria	0.038±0.005 a	0.011±0.005 b	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Litter Saprotroph	13.55±1.37 b	21.01±2.13 a	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Arbuscular Mycorrhiza	2.48±0.46 a	0.55±0.10 b	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Dung Saprotroph	1.86±0.15 a	0.68±0.15 b	-	-	-	-	-	-
	NT	NT+CC	NT X Block 1	NT X Block 2	NT X Block 3	NT+CC X Block 1	NT+CC X Block 2	NT+CC X Block 3	
Lithuania	Perennials (%)	ns	ns	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Specific Leaf Area (m ² g ⁻¹)	ns	ns	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Grass-like	ns	ns	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Fermentation	ns	Ns	2.55±0.91 a	2.45±0.9 b	2.08±0.07 a	2.69±0.10 a	3.46 ±0.12 a	2.00 ±0.07 a
	NP Cyanobacteria	ns	Ns	0.103±0.031 a	0.000±0.031 b	0.154±0.031 a	0.071±0.031 a	0.109±0.031 a	0.000±0.031 b
	Litter Saprotroph	ns	Ns	-	-	-	-	-	-
Arbuscular Mycorrhiza	0.10±0.03 a	0.06±0.03 a	0.24±0.05 a	0.00±0.05 a	0.07±0.05 a	0.03±0.05 b	0.10±0.05 a	0.03±0.05 a	

382	Dung Saprotroph	ns	Ns	-	-	-	-	-	-
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ns= not significant; -= factors or interactions not included in the regression model (See Table 4); Nd= functional trait/group not detected in the site.

383 4. Discussion

384 4.1 Is functional diversity relevant in explaining the variance of soil organic carbon and
385 water extractable carbon in agricultural fields?

386 A substantial body of literature has emphasized the critical role of biodiversity in ecosystem stability
387 and the provision of ES (e.g. Mace et al., 2012; Ricketts et al., 2016; Nizamani et al., 2024). C cycling
388 and storage is among the most important ESs in the context of climate change and in view of
389 sustainable agriculture production. Soil biota and plant diversity influence soil C dynamics through
390 complex interactions that govern SOC degradation, CO₂ emission, and SOC stabilization processes
391 (Adhikari & Hartemink, 2016). Our results highlighted that about 60% of the SOC and WEOC variation
392 across seven European and Turkish experimental sites was explained by plant functional traits and
393 microbial functional groups. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to adopt a functional
394 approach in studying the combined role of plant and microbial communities in SOC dynamics. Previous
395 research has generally focused on diversity indices or specific taxa. As an example, Lange et al. 2015,
396 found that microbial diversity explained 21% of soil C, with plant diversity significantly influencing this
397 relationship. Similarly, plant species richness accounted for 16%, 12%, and 17% of the variance in SOC
398 in Chinese forests, shrublands, and grasslands, respectively (Chen et al., 2018). In contrast, some
399 studies have suggested that plant traits are poor predictors of ecosystem properties, including SOC.
400 Only 12% of the variation in ecosystem properties was explained by plant traits and it dropped to less
401 than 5% when a reduced set of six traits was considered, which is very common in the literature (van
402 der Plas et al., 2020). Our results contradicted this finding. The high variance of SOC explained by the
403 functional diversity found in this study likely results from the inclusion of a comprehensive set of
404 functional traits/groups in our analysis (23 in total - six plant functional traits, ten bacterial and seven
405 fungal functional groups, respectively).

406 4.2 Given the complexity of the functional microbial groups and plants’ traits, how do
407 they interact in the context of SOC processes?

408 The intricated interplay between plant and soil microorganisms is strongly mediated by root exudates,
409 amount and quality of the plant residues. Plant traits play a critical role in shaping these interactions
410 by chemically and morphologically determining the amount and quality of plant inputs to soil. These
411 inputs, in turn, influence habitat conditions and resource availability for soil microbial biodiversity (De
412 Vries et al., 2012). Although PLS-SEM model explained 50% of the SOC variance, it did not show any
413 significant direct effect of plant traits on SOC (Figure 2). Trait-based approach has been proposed as a
414 key approach to study, monitor, and foster C accumulation in contrasting biomes. Different
415 environmental and anthropic factors and their interactions, however, determine SOC accumulation in

416 soils (De Deyn et al., 2008). Among biotic factors, root traits are often identified as the primary traits
417 affecting SOC accumulation (Lange et al., 2015; Poirier et al., 2018). These traits, however, are
418 challenging to measure and are among the least represented in plant trait datasets. In this study we
419 used plant height, taproot , perennial, and SAM traits as a proxy for root length and development, C
420 storage ability in the soil, and plant-mycorrhizal interaction. Nonetheless, the lack of specific root traits
421 in our analysis may also explain the non-significant direct effect of plant functional groups on SOC.

422 We also found a significant negative effect of the plant traits construct - comprised by SLA, Perennials
423 and Grass-like species- on the fungal functional group construct - consisting in arbuscular mycorrhiza,
424 litter and dung saprophytic fungi. To the best of our knowledge no study investigated the effects of
425 plant traits on microbial functional groups in agroecosystems. However, research in grasslands has
426 shown that distinct grass and forb groups, which exhibit different root traits, structured saprophytic
427 fungal communities (Francioli et al., 2021). Grass-like species provide residues with high C:N ratio and
428 lignin concentration which are potentially degradable by the saprophytic communities. Nevertheless
429 an excessive availability of C coupled with low mineral N soil concentrations can have a depressive
430 effect on the abundance of fungal and bacterial communities. Studies have also shown that
431 saprophytic communities are sensitive to soil stoichiometry, particularly the C:N and N:P ratios,
432 highlighting the critical role of soil N levels in determining the saprophytic community structure and
433 development (Ning et al., 2021). SLA is associated with plants exhibiting high metabolic activity,
434 allowing rapid investment in leaf area and typically found in highly disturbed environments (Kazakou
435 et al., 2016). A high SLA corresponds to a large photosynthetic area and a low biomass weight,
436 associated with “fast” leaf economic spectrum characterised by less dense and more water-rich
437 leaves, which translate into a low dry matter, C-poor residues (Reich, 2014). These residues promote
438 rapid decomposition by bacteria (Strickland & Rousk, 2010), which may compete with saprotrophic
439 and mycorrhizal fungi for available nutrients. Similarly, perennials plants can contribute little to plant
440 residues accumulation. Retranslocation of leaves nitrogen to rhizomes before senescence reduces the
441 C:N ratio of the aboveground litter, influencing decomposition rates (Berardi et al., 2024).
442 Consequently, plant communities with high SLA and perennial traits may exert a depressive effect on
443 saprophytic fungi, which generally thrive in litter and C-rich environments (Liu et al., 2023).

444 Arbuscular mycorrhiza were also included in the fungal functional groups construct which was
445 negatively influenced by the plant functional traits and, in turn, had a negative effect on SOC (Figure
446 2). Arbuscular mycorrhizae exert a dual influence on SOC. On the one hand they can transport C into
447 soils through the mycelium development thereby positively affecting SOC. It has been argued that
448 arbuscular mycorrhiza represents an important soil C pool as the global plant community allocate 3.93
449 Gt CO₂e per year to arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (Hawkins et al., 2023). Mycorrhiza can further

450 improve SOC by stimulating soil aggregation through the exudation of glomalin related soil protein,
451 and the microbial necromass turnover (Zhou et al., 2024). On the other hand, the N acquisition of
452 arbuscular mycorrhizae indirectly affect SOC dynamics. Unlike decomposers, arbuscular mycorrhiza
453 do not directly obtain N from soil organic matter; instead, they rely on decomposers to access the
454 essential N (Wurzburger & Brookshire, 2017). Synergistic relationship between arbuscular mycorrhiza
455 and saprotrophic fungi were reported in the literature and are very consistent with our results.
456 Arbuscular mycorrhiza can stimulate the saprotrophic communities, enhancing the enzyme activity
457 and indirectly accelerating the organic matter mineralization, particularly in N-poor soils (Cao et al.,
458 2022). In our study samples were collected at the stage of maximum nutrient uptake of the crops. In
459 this context competing claims for N from crops and arbuscular mycorrhiza could have stimulated the
460 synergy between arbuscular mycorrhiza and soil saprotroph, ultimately leading to a reduction in the
461 SOC pool. However, the observed decrease in SOC during the sampling period may be transient and
462 could potentially be mitigated—or even reversed—by subsequent mycelial development and the
463 turnover of associated microbial necromass.

464 We also observed a significant negative influence of plant traits on bacterial functional groups, which
465 in turn negatively impacted SOC. The reductive effect of bacterial groups on SOC was more
466 pronounced than that of fungi. As previously discussed for fungal groups, plant diversity has a strong
467 influence on soil microbial communities, including bacterial functional groups (Berg & Smalla, 2009).
468 Non-photosynthetic cyanobacteria were among the bacterial functional groups influenced by
469 vegetation that exhibited a negative impact on SOC. Although it is known that non photosynthetic
470 cyanobacteria require large C pools to growth, studies on the effects of non-photosynthetic
471 cyanobacteria on soil C degradation are still lacking (Cano-Díaz et al., 2020). According to these
472 authors, various taxa of non-photosynthetic cyanobacteria inhabit a wide range of climates, including
473 mesic forests, hyper-arid deserts, and temperate and dry grasslands. Overall, our findings align with
474 the metanalysis by Trivedi et al. (2016) which reported a negative correlation between SOC and certain
475 cyanobacteria taxa especially in dry areas. Fermentation-associated bacteria were also among the
476 bacterial functional groups influenced by vegetation traits that exhibited a negative impact on SOC.
477 Fermentation bacteria are known decomposers in agricultural soils, playing an important role in
478 organic matter degradation, thereby contributing to the organic matter turnover (Wu et al., 2024).
479 Due to their metabolic activity, fermentation bacteria have been also used and selected for various
480 biotechnological applications (Olle, 2021). Fermentation process of soil organic matter represent the
481 key process for organic matter turnover in paddy rice and for this reason they are often associated
482 with methanogenesis and denitrification communities (Liesack et al., 2000; Wu et al., 2024).

483 Nevertheless fermentation bacteria can still play a role in C degradation in not-submerged soils where
484 anoxic areas can be found across the profile (Lacroix et al., 2023).

485 [4.3 Do farming practices play an effect on the plants and microbial functional groups?](#)
486 Farming practices including variable degrees of tillage, fertilization, and diversification techniques
487 induce chemical and physical changes which alter soil conditions. Our results showed that the
488 aggregation of traits from plant and microbial communities was significantly affected by farm
489 management (Figure 3; Table 3). Evidence from the literature confirm that farming practices affects
490 soil biodiversity at different taxonomic scales: from the larger taxonomic groups to the species level,
491 till the functional groups (Bàrberi et al., 2018; Cozim-Melges et al., 2024; de Graaff et al., 2019; Wood
492 et al., 2015). Farming practices should, therefore, be conceptualized as environmental filters able to
493 modulate the functionality of plant and soil microbial diversity, ultimately mediating both agronomic
494 outcomes and ecosystem functioning (de la Riva et al., 2023; Ryan et al., 2010).

495 [4.4 What is the impact of farming practices on the plant functional traits and microbial](#)
496 [groups that are relevant for SOC turnover?](#)

497 This study identified the most relevant functional units that mediated to SOC changes (Figure 2). Then,
498 we tested how specific farming practices affected these functional groups, using a subset of data of
499 three sites across Europe (Table 5).

500 Across these sites we found that farming practices affected perennial trait only in Italy. Specifically,
501 perennial plant cover was higher under INC management compared to ICC. The results is not surprising
502 as the cover crop – which are annual plant species- were also included in the data analysis.
503 Nevertheless, perennial plants benefit from undisturbed or less disturbed environments (e.g. no tillage
504 in INC), where they can express their colonizing potential (Alarcón et al., 2018; Anderson, 2015).

505 In Italy, the higher SLA under INC compared to ICC (Table 5) was in line with Ciaccia et al. (2020), who
506 observed that perennial plants increase under untilled INC indirectly favoured plant communities with
507 high resource-use ability. Additionally, the repetitive mowing used to terminate weed biomass, as
508 implemented in INC, was shown to select grass-like species with rapid regeneration, which typically
509 exhibit high SLA values (Nichols et al., 2015).

510 Concerning the bacterial community, diversification practices increased the abundance of
511 fermentation bacteria. Specifically, fermentation bacteria were higher under cover cropping in Italy
512 and Lithuania (only in one block) and in Spain under crop rotation (only in one block) (Table 5). We
513 hypothesized that a higher fresh organic matter input from the cover crops could have increased
514 resources for the bacterial fermentation community, thereby fostering their growth and activity.

515 Similarly, in Spain plant biomass was higher under crop rotation and could have had a beneficial effect
516 on the microbial community.

517 Diversification practices had a variable effect on the abundance of non-photosynthetic cyanobacteria.
518 In Italy, their abundance was higher under cover cropping, whereas in Spain it was lower under crop
519 rotation (Table 5). At the Italian site, the presence of an N-fixing crop (vetch) may have stimulated the
520 non-photosynthetic cyanobacterial community, whose role in nitrogen dynamics has been
521 documented in the literature (e.g. Ibrahim & El-Sawah, 2022). In contrast, the results from Spain did
522 not align with existing literature. Navarro-Noya et al. (2013) reported that crop residue management
523 influences bacterial communities but found no effect from crop rotation. Similarly, the metanalysis by
524 Venter et al. (2016) on crop rotation effects on soil microbial communities reported inconsistent
525 results, even when legumes were included in rotations. In Lithuania, the effects of treatments on non-
526 photosynthetic cyanobacteria were inconsistent across experimental blocks, precluding further
527 conclusions (Table 5).

528 Fungal abundance in carbon-degrading functional groups is often linked to the availability of
529 substrates for degradation. The quality and availability of fresh organic matter inputs, as well as the
530 disturbance factors in edaphic habitats, are ultimately shaped by agronomic practices (e.g., tillage
531 type, cover cropping). Unexpectedly we did not observe any significant effect of cover cropping on
532 litter saprotroph and inconsistent results on dung saprotroph (Table 5). Our results are not in
533 agreement with the literature, which reported marked increases in the saprotrophic community under
534 cover cropping (Hallama et al., 2022; Schmidt et al., 2019; Vukicevich et al., 2016). However, at the
535 Spanish site, we observed that crop rotation had a (i) reductive effect on dung saprotrophic fungi and
536 a (ii) significant positive effect on litter saprotrophic fungi, likely due to the higher aboveground
537 biomass in these plots compared to wheat monoculture. Indeed, a high correlation among wheat
538 biomass, soil respiration and saprotrophs was reported in a 30-year legume- and non-legume-based
539 winter wheat rotations in the Chinese drylands (Wang et al., 2023). Additionally, Orrù et al. (2021)
540 found that crop rotation significantly influenced the biodiversity of saprophytic fungi. These results
541 further support the stimulating and selective effect of crop rotation on the saprophytic community
542 found at the Spanish site.

543 Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi are essential for plant health and play a key role in soil organic carbon
544 (SOC) dynamics. Their abundance and potential for infecting plant roots are strongly influenced by
545 edaphic conditions, plant traits, and soil disturbance. Our results indicated a lower abundance of
546 arbuscular mycorrhiza across all three sites following diversification practices (Table 5). In both the
547 Italian and Lithuanian sites treatment effects were significant in only one block), cover cropping

548 reduced arbuscular mycorrhizal abundance. In these sites, cover crop treatments were compared with
549 no-tillage practices. Arbuscular mycorrhizae are known to be highly sensitive to tillage, with studies
550 reporting higher abundance and diversity under no-tillage systems compared to conventional tillage
551 (Brito et al., 2012; Moitinho et al., 2020). Since cover crop sowing typically requires at least two tillage
552 operations, we hypothesized that the tillage associated with the sowing process may have reduced
553 the abundance of arbuscular mycorrhiza in Italian site. In the case of Lithuania, Persian clovers were
554 sown early in the spring (at the renewal oilseed rape vegetation) on the soil surface without disturbing
555 the soil using a fertilizer spreader. However, after harvesting, clover plants constituted less than 10%
556 from all soil covering plants, while brassica volunteer plants made up close to 90%. Therefore, we
557 believe, there may be a side effect of oilseed rape, which is known as a non-mycorrhizal crop (Yu et al
558 2020).

559 5. Conclusion

560 This study employed a functional approach to examine the combined roles of plant and microbial
561 communities in SOC dynamics across seven sites in Europe and Turkey. To our knowledge, this is the
562 first study tackling the complexity of SOC dynamics through the emerging lens of plant, bacterial, and
563 fungal functional biodiversity. We demonstrated that functional diversity is crucial in explaining the
564 variability of SOC in agricultural soils. This study also identified plant traits and functional microbial
565 groups which are critical to SOC and shed lights on their complex interactions. In this context
566 farming practices act as key environmental filters, influencing the functionality of both plant and
567 microbial communities, and thereby shaping ecosystem processes and agricultural outcomes.

568 These results have profound implications for future research. Methodologically, the research
569 underscores the importance of adopting a functional approach to better understand the complex
570 interactions driving SOC dynamics. It calls for advancing soil biodiversity knowledge, particularly with
571 respect to the functional relevance of microorganisms. From a modelling perspective, this study
572 suggests that functional diversity should be integrated in SOC modelling efforts to better monitor and
573 predict SOC changes across time and space. Lastly, it highlights the need to consider the impact of
574 farming practices on functional diversity when designing sustainable soil management at different
575 scales (field, farm, landscape). A deeper understanding of these interactions can guide the
576 development of strategies for managing biodiversity to simultaneously promote environmental
577 sustainability and agricultural productivity.

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582 [research/agroecoseqc](https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/agroecoseqc)

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